

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP5 – Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public

D5.12 Annual report on external communications for impact assessment January- December 2021

Lead contributor	Stéphanie Tcherny-Lessenot (39 – Sanofi)
Other contributors	Stéphanie Tcherny-Lessenot (39 – Sanofi) Sally Stephens (12- UNEW) Alison Oliver (12- UNEW) Agnes Kant (9 – Stichting Lareb) Ulrika Nörby (29 – Region Stockholm) Ludivine Douarin (39 – Sanofi) Michael Steel (38- Novartis)

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Abstract

The main aim of WP5 is to improve the value, quality and harmonisation of the dissemination of information on the available evidence related to medicines use in pregnancy and during breastfeeding.

The 5.3 sub-task aim is to engage HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public to stimulate pregnancy reporting through PV systems, by increasing their awareness that they can play an active role in increasing general knowledge about the safety of drug use during pregnancy and breastfeeding

The objective of this report is to summarize communication actions performed in WP5 to disseminate knowledge about medicines use during pregnancy and lactation and to engage pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals (HCPs) in the ConcePTION ecosystem between January and December 2021. The communications actions may have different targets and different messages.

For this report on the third year of the project, the main communication activities were related to raising awareness on safe use of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding, stimulating reporting and promoting enrolment in local registries part of local pilots in the UK and the Netherlands.

Methods

The objective of the report is to make an inventory of communication actions performed in WP5 on the third year of the project.

The communication actions are classified by their objective:

- Engagement of pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals in the ConcePTION ecosystem
- Increase awareness and stimulate reporting on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The communications actions are grouped by objective and are described using the following parameters: the geographical reach, the target audience, the channel used, the date of dissemination, and the main presenter.

Results

The communication actions for this report are divided into three main groups:

- General information and targeted actions
 - o to raise awareness on the knowledge bank
 - o to stimulate reporting via different channels
- Targeted actions to stimulate enrolment in pREGnant registry in the Netherlands
- Targeted actions to stimulate enrolment in BUMPS registry in the UK

The targeted actions in the Netherlands and in the UK are described in the Wp 5.3 D5.2 deliverable: Report describing communication plan and governance.

Actions to raise awareness on the knowledge bank were conducted through web communication and use of social media in various European countries and reaching international organizations. Moreover, one communication was posted in April 2021 on ELEVATE Health website to raise awareness on healthcare provider learning platform.

ConcePTION channels have a small following, but a large organic reach. They include a website (www.imi-conception.eu), a Twitter handle, <https://twitter.com/IMIConception> (371 followers 16 March 2022), a LinkedIn profile, www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception/ (followers 22 March) and an e-mail newsletter audience (launched in December 2021 with 253 recipients. The audience has grown 45% in 3 months, currently reaching 558 subscribers), and an organic reach that extended to a total of 6224 opens of the first mailing (sent to 253 individuals).

Table 1: Communication actions to raise awareness on knowledge bank

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) International Women's Day	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
Global	Women, health care professionals	Web (post in ConcePTION news)	March 2021	Josepine Fernow
Global	Women, health care professionals	Web (post in ConcePTION news)	June 2021	Anna Holm
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	July 2021	IMIConception
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	August 2021	IMIConception
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	October 2021	IMIConception
Global	Women, health care professionals	Web (post in ConcePTION news at medsafetyweek)	November 2021	Helena Harnik
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	December 2021	IMIConception

Actions to stimulate reporting of exposure during pregnancy were conducted through web communication and use of social media in various European countries and reaching international organizations.

Table 2: Communication actions to stimulate reporting of exposure during pregnancy and breastfeeding

Country/ Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals	Webinar on pregnancy reporting	February 2021	Christine Taeter UCB, Luke Richardson ENTIS, Helen Dolk EUROCAT
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	March 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals	Web (post in ConcePTION news)	April 2021	Ida Niklson
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	April 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	May 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	June 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	July 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals	Website landing page with information about PV reporting	April 2021	Josepine Fernow
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	August 2021	IMIConcePTION Women, health care professionals
Global	Women, health care professionals	Web (post in ConcePTION news on world patient safety day)	September 2021	Josepine Fernow
Global	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	November 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women	Social media (twitter) campaign for the Uppsala Monitoring Centres MedSafetyWeek	November 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women	Social media (twitter) campaign for Safe Motherhood Week	November 2021	IMIConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	E-mail newsletter with invitation to workshop on	December 2021	IMIConcePTION

		pharmacovigilance in pregnancy		
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (LinkedIn) publicity for workshop on pharmacovigilance in pregnancy	December 2021	IMIconcePTION

The communications actions to raise awareness on the knowledge bank and to stimulate reporting have been conducted by task 5.3 members with support of ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (twitter campaigns (<https://twitter.com/IMIconcePTION>), web posts (https://www.imi-conception.eu/news-details/?news_id=816), webinar, etc).

Targeted communication actions to stimulate enrolment in pREGnant registry in the Netherlands were conducted through web communication and use of social media and through health documentation used for COVID-19 vaccination.

Table 3: Targeted communication actions to stimulate reporting and enrolment in pREGnant registry in the Netherlands

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Netherlands	Women	National news item	January 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Social media (Facebook Lareb)	January 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Paper (call to action at the health certificate needed before COVID-19 vaccination)	Whole 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Web (post on 22-weeks vaccination against whooping cough on website National Institute of Public Health and Environment)	Whole 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Podcast (sponsoring podcast pregnancy week 6, 7, 8 "24Baby")	May-December 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Web (10 articles on website for pregnant women, "Zwangerenportaal")	May-December 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Web (banners/ads on website for pregnant women, "Zwangerenportaal")	May-December 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Web (7 articles on website for pregnant women, "24Baby")	May-December 2021	Lareb
Netherlands	Women	Web (banners/ads on website for pregnant women, "24Baby")	May-December 2021	Lareb

Targeted communication actions to stimulate enrolment in BUMPS registry in the UK were conducted through web communication and use of various social media (Twitter, Instagram, Facebook and Youtube).

Table 4: Targeted communication actions to stimulate reporting and enrolment in BUMPS registry in the UK

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (repeated twitter)	January 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) International Epilepsy Day	February 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) CHD awareness week	February 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) CHD awareness week	February 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Web: Blog in BUMPS website (Introduction to BUMPS)	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (repeated twitter)	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) World Birth Defects Day	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) World Kidney Day	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) World Kidney Day	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) British Science Week	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) British Science Week	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Web: Blog in BUMPS website (MS conversation)	March 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) MS awareness week	April 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) UK Maternal Mental Health Awareness week	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) International Day of the Midwife	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) International Day of the Midwife	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) Mental Health Awareness week	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) Mental Health Awareness week	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) IMI ConcePTION blog announcement	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women, health care professionals	Web: Blog in BUMPS website (IMI ConcePTION)	May 2021	UKTIS Bumps
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) British Heart Week	June 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) British Heart Week	June 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women	Social media (Instagram) Diabetes week	June 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) Diabetes week	June 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women	Social Media (Facebook) Diabetes week	June 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women	Social Media (Instagram) Announcement of Blog in BUMPS website (Pharmacovigilance)	July 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Web: Women, health care professionals	Blog in BUMPS website (Pharmacovigilance)	July 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women	Social Media (Facebook) Pharmacovigilance	July 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women	Social media (twitter) World Patient Safety day	September 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Web: Women, health care professionals	Web: Blog in BUMPS website (COVID19)	October 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter) World Prematurity Day	November 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (Youtube) Teratology video	December 2021	UKTIS BUMPS
UK	Women, health care professionals	Social media (twitter)	December 2021	UKTIS BUMPS

Discussion and Conclusion

In the third year of the project, the communication efforts were focused on raising awareness on medicines use during pregnancy and breastfeeding, stimulating reporting and promoting enrolment in local registries part of local pilots in the UK and the Netherlands.

For future reports, we will consider to add some metrics on the different activities.